

Analysis of the Critical Calculation Speed in the Curves of Federal Roads (Category B) in Two Austrian Federal States

Abstract

Curves on federal roads pose a significant challenge to traffic safety. In particular, tight curve radii and insufficiently adjusted design speeds are associated with an increased accident risk. This study analyzes the critical (permissible) calculation speed (V_{crit}) in curves and its relationship with accident frequency as well as road infrastructure. Based on a 12-year data analysis of federal roads (Category B) in two Austrian federal states, key parameters such as curve radius, cross slope, and measured friction coefficients (μ) are examined. The results indicate that traditional models for design speed systematically underestimate the actual risks in curves. A new classification model for assessing critical curve speeds is introduced, enabling an improved evaluation of high-risk areas. This leads to concrete recommendations for optimizing road infrastructure and enhancing traffic safety.

Keywords: Curve safety; critical speed; road geometry; accident analysis; traffic safety; neural networks; classification models

1 Introduction

Curves on rural roads are among the most accident-prone areas of the road network, significantly impacting vehicle stability and driver control. Numerous studies (Bauer and Harwood [1]; De Oña and Garach [2]; Buddhavarapu et al. [3]) have emphasized the role of geometric design and environmental conditions in influencing accident rates. However, thresholds and variable interactions remain inconsistent, underscoring the need for localized studies.

This paper addresses these gaps specifically for Austrian rural federal roads by analyzing the relationship between geometric road features, surface friction conditions, and critical speed on accident risk, proposing new classification models using statistical and machine learning techniques.

2 Literature Review

Curves on rural roads are among the most accident-prone areas of the road network, as they significantly impact vehicle stability and driver control. Numerous studies have examined the relationship between curve geometry and accident frequency, emphasizing the importance of factors such as curve radius, superelevation, friction, and driver perception.

2.1 Impact of Curve Geometry on Safety

The influence of curve radius on accident risk has been extensively studied. Research confirms that smaller radii ($R < 200$ m) significantly increase accident likelihood, with the probability nearly doubling for radii below 125 m (Bauer and Harwood [1]; De Oña and Garach [2]). This is due to the higher lateral forces acting on vehicles, which increase the risk of skidding or overturning.

The models by Bauer and Harwood [1] show that accident frequency increases with decreasing horizontal curve radius, decreasing curve length, and increasing grade percentage. The interaction between tight, short curves and steep gradients results in the highest crash rates.

Superelevation plays a crucial role in mitigating lateral forces in curves. Studies by Fitzpatrick et al. [4] and Glennon [5] indicate that insufficient superelevation ($<2\%$) results in higher accident rates, particularly under wet road conditions. Research revealed that sections with inadequate superelevation experienced significantly more accidents compared to properly designed sections (Glennon [5]).

2.2 Role of Road Surface Friction in Curve Safety

Road surface friction is a fundamental factor in determining vehicle stability, especially in curves. Numerous studies confirm that low friction values, particularly below 0.35, substantially increase accident risk under wet or icy conditions.

Buddhavarapu, Banerjee, and Prozzi [3] found that pavement surface condition has a stronger influence on crash occurrence in curves than general skid resistance indices, especially on rural two-lane roads. Their research showed that crash rates increase disproportionately as surface friction deteriorates.

Complementary to these findings, Hall, Smith, and Littleton [6] demonstrated that skid resistance plays a critical role in maintaining vehicle control during curve negotiation. Their work emphasized that systematic pavement friction monitoring and targeted surface treatments are essential for maintaining curve safety, particularly under adverse weather conditions.

Regarding vehicle type, Gillespie [7] showed that passenger cars require significantly higher lateral friction coefficients than heavy trucks due to differences in weight distribution and dynamic response. This difference makes cars more vulnerable to loss of control when surface friction is insufficient, highlighting the importance of considering vehicle-specific dynamics in curve safety assessments.

These findings collectively underline the necessity of real-time surface monitoring, preventive maintenance, and context-sensitive pavement design to improve road safety in horizontal curves.

2.3 Speed Management and Risk Perception in Curves

Driver speed behavior in curves often deviates significantly from design expectations, contributing to

increased crash risks. Traditional design models usually assume that drivers comply with posted speed limits; however, empirical evidence demonstrates that actual operating speeds often exceed both design and posted speeds, particularly in rural curves.

De Oña and Garach [2] reported that actual speeds in curves are typically 5–12 km/h higher than the theoretical design speed, significantly raising accident probability. The discrepancy between perceived and actual safe speeds becomes especially hazardous on curves with reduced sight distances and compromised friction conditions.

Advanced technologies offer promising countermeasures. Li et al. [8] developed a variable speed limit (VSL) strategy that dynamically adjusts posted speeds based on real-time weather and traffic conditions. Their findings demonstrated that VSL systems could reduce secondary crash risks by up to 20% under adverse weather conditions, highlighting the importance of adaptive speed control measures in enhancing curve safety.

These insights underscore the necessity of integrating real-world driver perception dynamics into curve safety management. Moving beyond static design speed assumptions towards responsive, context-sensitive speed management systems is essential for mitigating crash risks in rural curves.

2.4 Implications for Traffic Safety Improvements

Improving curve safety requires an integrated approach that considers geometric, environmental, and behavioral factors. Various studies emphasize that a combination of dynamic speed management, real-time friction monitoring, and optimized geometric design can significantly reduce accident risk in curves.

Fitzpatrick, Carlson, and Brewer [4] demonstrated that implementing dynamic speed adaptation strategies — such as variable speed limits based on road and weather conditions — substantially reduces crash occurrences on rural highways. Their findings underline the effectiveness of context-sensitive speed control interventions tailored to site-specific risk factors.

In addition, Hall, Smith, and Littleton [6] highlighted that continuous monitoring of pavement friction and timely surface treatments (e.g., high-friction surface treatments at critical curve locations) can markedly enhance curve safety, especially under adverse weather conditions.

Future safety strategies should leverage emerging technologies such as artificial intelligence (AI) and connected vehicle data. Zhang and Abdel-Aty [9] showed that machine learning models utilizing real-time vehicle telemetry can dynamically assess and predict crash risks on curves, offering a proactive means to identify high-risk sites before accidents occur.

Collectively, these studies support a proactive, adaptive approach to curve safety that moves beyond

traditional static road design and speed setting practices, integrating continuous risk assessment and real-time operational management.

2.5 Critical Review of Existing Studies

Previous studies have firmly established the relationships between curve radius, road surface friction, cross slope, and crash risk. However, considerable inconsistencies remain regarding the critical thresholds and relative importance of these factors.

Bauer and Harwood [1] showed that curve radii below 125 meters substantially increase crash frequency, particularly when combined with steep grades and inadequate superelevation. In contrast, De Oña and Garach [2] found that accident risks begin rising at curve radii under 200 meters, suggesting that local traffic compositions, environmental conditions, and driver behaviors heavily influence risk thresholds.

Moreover, conventional geometric design models often assume static vehicle-road interaction characteristics. Yet, recent research using real-world telemetry and connected vehicle data (Zhang and Abdel-Aty [9]) demonstrates that driver behavior is highly dynamic and context-sensitive, especially in curves. Traditional Crash Modification Factors (CMFs) (Cafiso et al. [10]) may therefore underestimate crash risks in complex curve environments where behavioral adaptations and environmental variables interact non-linearly.

Another important gap is the limited integration of driver risk perception into safety models. While technologies such as Advanced Curve Speed Warning Systems (A-CSW) (Li et al. [8]) show promising potential to mitigate speeding and improve curve navigation, their widespread implementation remains limited, and their effectiveness under diverse environmental conditions is not yet fully validated.

These discrepancies highlight the urgent need for comprehensive curve safety models that combine geometric, environmental, and behavioral factors. Such integrated frameworks would better reflect real-world complexities and enable more effective proactive safety management strategies.

2.6 Theoretical Framework

This study is grounded in the principles of the Safe System Approach, which emphasizes the necessity of designing road environments that proactively account for human error and vulnerability. Unlike traditional models that often place the burden of crash prevention on individual drivers, the Safe System philosophy promotes a holistic view where road design, vehicle capabilities, enforcement, and environmental conditions collectively ensure road user safety.

According to the Safe System framework articulated by OECD/ITF [11], roads should be "forgiving" — meaning that inevitable human mistakes should not lead to severe or fatal outcomes. In the context of horizontal curves, this implies that geometric features such as curve radius, superelevation, and friction must be carefully aligned with typical operating speeds and driver behavior.

Additionally, concepts from Risk Homeostasis Theory, proposed by Wilde [12], inform this study. Risk Homeostasis suggests that drivers adapt their behavior based on perceived safety margins: when drivers perceive an increase in safety (e.g., better road surfaces or wider lanes), they may subconsciously increase their speed or reduce vigilance, thus offsetting the intended safety benefits.

Empirical research by DeJoy [13] further supports the notion that drivers adjust risk-taking behavior in response to perceived roadway conditions, emphasizing that infrastructure improvements must be coupled with behavioral interventions to achieve true safety gains.

By integrating road geometric characteristics, surface friction conditions, and dynamic driver behavior patterns into machine learning-based predictive models, this study aims to operationalize the Safe System principles and extend them into practical curve safety management frameworks.

3 Methodology

3.1 Flowchart of the procedure applied in the proposed research

Figure 1a and Figure 1b illustrate the workflow for the evaluation and analysis of accident hotspots. Details on each step can be found in the following subsections.

Figure 1a: Flowchart (Workflow) for the Analysis of Accident Hotspots – First Part.

Figure 1b: Flowchart (Workflow) for the Analysis of Accident Hotspots – Second Part (Continuation).

3.2 Study Areas

For this study, 1,538 km of federal roads B in two Austrian federal states and 1,025 km of federal roads B in another Austrian federal state were analyzed, totaling 2,563 road kilometers. A total of 2,111 curve-related accidents from the first state and 1,222 curve-related accidents from the second state were examined, resulting in a total of 3,333 curve-related accidents.

3.3 Geometric Properties of Federal Roads B

The federal roads B examined in this study belong to the road type 'main traffic roads.' According to RVS [14], the minimum horizontal radius for Austrian federal roads B is:

- the minimum radius: $\min R = 200$ m,
- the maximum longitudinal slope: $\max S = 8\%$,
- the minimum cross slope: $\min q = 2.5\%$,
- the maximum cross slope: $\max q = 7\%$.

3.4 Crash data

The accident data was provided by the Austrian Institute of Technology (AIT) and originates from Statistic Austria. This dataset includes police-reported curve-related accidents involving personal injuries, specifically for accident types 012, 013, 022, 023, 222, 223, 225, 226, 232, 242, 265, and 266 (Table 1).

Table 1: Accidents in Open Country on Category B Federal Roads (2012–2023) by Accident Type (Curve Accidents). Own Representation According to Vogel [15].

Accident types (curves)	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
12 Run-off road to the right, in right curve	101	92	96	84	87	99	88	87	84	81	71	73
13 Run-off road to the right, in left curve	364	374	356	331	374	314	369	335	313	293	292	330
22 Run-off road to the left, in right curve	189	171	175	155	171	172	182	162	128	134	148	148
23 Run-off road to the left, in left curve	82	80	72	75	61	82	65	67	43	39	38	59
222 Run-off road to the right due to oncoming vehicle, in right curve	12	7	6	5	8	4	3	4	1	1	-	3
223 Run-off road to the right due to oncoming vehicle, in left curve	16	8	5	6	13	11	8	6	5	5	1	2
225 Run-off road to the left due to oncoming vehicle, in right curve	50	38	41	34	39	34	3	4	2	-	1	3
226 Run-off road to the left due to oncoming vehicle, in left curve	20	20	12	21	10	9	-	-	2	-	-	1
232 Side collision, in a curve	60	76	65	62	68	55	91	94	81	73	98	104
242 Head-on collision, in a curve	96	80	62	70	72	76	146	143	110	110	120	122
265 Head-on or side collision while overtaking, in right curve	7	6	12	10	15	10	19	23	14	13	15	18
266 Head-on or side collision while overtaking, in left curve	4	5	3	8	6	4	11	6	8	7	8	5
Total	1,001	957	905	861	924	870	985	931	791	756	792	868

3.5 Annual average daily traffic, AADT

The data on AADT was provided by the respective state governments of two Austrian federal states. Additionally, traffic volume data was retrieved from the respective state authorities.

3.6 RoadSTAR Data

Two Austrian federal states were selected for the study because a higher-quality collection of RoadSTAR data was provided by AIT. Using the RoadSTAR mobile laboratory, which delivers excellent data in terms of quality, resolution, and coverage, dGPS coordinates (Differential Global Positioning System) can also be generated. These, along with alignment parameters and curve curvature, serve as input parameters for extensive analyses. The total number of RoadSTAR data records included in the study is 4,287,602.

With RoadSTAR [16], the following parameters, among others, can be recorded: traveled distance s (m), $StrKM$ – road kilometer, GPS coordinates, 1m friction mean value μ (-), 1m mean value of road surface temperature T (°C), 1m texture mean value MPD (mm), 1m longitudinal evenness index IRI (-), cracks (linear + area-related) summarized in relation to image area [%], surface damage summarized in relation to image area [%], 1m mean value of cross slope q (%), 1m mean value of longitudinal slope s (%), 1m mean value of curve radius R (m), 1m mean value of clothoid parameter A , 1m mean value of curvature for a 1,000 m section length, measurement date, start time of the measurement, and much more.

3.7 Accident Cost Rates

Accident cost rates (ACR) assess accident risk based on accident consequences. They describe the average economic costs incurred due to road traffic accidents per 1,000 vehicle-kilometers traveled on a specific road section [17] [Eq. 1]:

$$ACR = \frac{AC \cdot 10^3}{AADT \cdot L \cdot 365 \cdot t} \text{ [€/1,000 vehicle-km]} \quad (\text{Eq. 1})$$

Where [17]:

AC	Accident Costs [€]
$AADT$	Annual Average Daily Traffic [vehicle/24h]
L	Length of the Road Section [km]
t	Analysis Period in Years [a]

3.8 Calculation of Critical Speed in Curves

The critical calculated speed (V_{crit}) is computed using [Eq. 2]:

$$V_{crit} = \sqrt{\frac{R \cdot g (\mu + q)}{1 - \mu \cdot q}} \quad (\text{Eq. 2})$$

Where:

R	= Curve radius (m)
g	= Gravitational acceleration (9.81 m/s ²)
μ	= Pavement friction coefficient
q	= Cross slope gradient

3.9 Determination of the Critical Speed in the Most Accident-Prone Curve with $R = 20$ m.

The determination of the critical speed in the curve with $R = 20$ m, $\mu = 0.67$, and $q = 5.7\%$ is shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Determination of the Critical Speed in the Most Accident-Prone Curve with $R = 20$ m.

Anony mRoad No	Station [KM]	Curve radius R [m]	Gravitation. acceleration g [m/s ²]	Friction coefficient μ	Cross slope gradien t q [%]	Speed limit [km/h]	Critical speed V_{crit} [km/h]	Difference between speed limit and V_{crit} [km/h]
B16	12.500	20.00	9.81	0.67	5.7	100	43.840	56.159

Table 2 shows that the critical (permissible) speed V_{crit} for the analyzed curve is 43.840 km/h. The difference between this speed and the speed limit of 100 km/h recorded in the accident data is an astonishing 56.159 km/h. Figure 2 illustrates the location of the road section with the highest accident

frequency. This area includes a curve with a radius of $R = 20$ m.

Figure 2 shows that, in increasing kilometrage, a straight section (marked by a long red arrow) is located directly before this curve (KM 12.500). This clearly indicates that the combination of a long straight section and a sharp curve is a key factor contributing to the accidents occurring at this location. Between 2012 and 2023, a total of 13 accidents occurred in this curve, representing the highest number of curve-related accidents among the analyzed 3,333 accidents.

Figure 2: Location of the Most Affected Accident Hotspot Section. Google Maps

In decreasing kilometrage, the discontinuous sequence of radii is clearly noticeable in Figure 2: A right-hand curve with a radius of $R = 224$ m is immediately followed by the accident-prone left-hand curve with a radius of $R = 20$ m. This results in a radius ratio of $R_1 : R_2 = 11.2$, whereas according to the guideline [14], a ratio of $R_1 : R_2 > 1.5$ is required.

Figure 3 shows this particularly accident-prone curve—a right-hand curve in increasing kilometrage—located at the end of the straight section.

Figure 3: The Most Accident-Prone Right-Hand Curve at the End of the Straight Section. Google Maps

Figure 4 shows the midpoint of this curve with $R = 20$ m.

Figure 4: View into the Curve Center with $R = 20$ m, approx. 12.500 KM. Google Maps.

4 Model Development

4.1 Variables

This analysis considers the following parameters:

- Curve radius R
- Measured friction coefficient (μ)
- Cross slope q
- Speed limit according to accident data
- Accident cost rate ACR

The calculated curve speed (V_{crit}) is determined using ORIGIN PRO. Missing speed limits are supplemented by the average value of the calculated and actual speed. The SPSS software generates the variable 'Safety' with two classes:

- ($V_{crit} \geq$ actual limit) \rightarrow 1 (safe)
- ($V_{crit} <$ actual limit) \rightarrow 0 (unsafe)

4.2 Classification Model: Binary Logistic Regression

A model for classifying curves as 'safe' or 'unsafe' is based on 354 cases without missing values. However, the logistic regression does not yield significant results, as it does not sufficiently explain variations in safety.

4.3 Regression Model for Speed Limit Optimization: Multiple Linear Regression

The analysis shows a significant but weak explanatory power ($R^2 = 4.5\%$). Only the accident cost rate has a significant impact on the speed limit, while other variables such as curve radius, road surface friction, and cross slope do not show a significant influence.

4.4 BAUM analysis in SPSS using the CRT (Classification and Regression Tree) method

4.4.1 Methodology

Since the previous models proved to be insufficient, a BAUM analysis was conducted in SPSS using the CRT (Classification and Regression Tree) method. This method provides a more precise decision basis by modeling safety as the dependent variable and identifying relevant influencing factors such as calculated speed, curve radius, and accident cost rate (Table 3).

Table 3: BAUM Analysis Using the CRT (Classification and Regression Tree) Method: Model Summary

Specifications	Growth method	CRT
	Dependent variable	<i>Safety</i>
	Independent variables	<i>Curve radius R, ACR - Accident cost rate, Road surface friction μ, Cross slope q, Calculated speed V_{crit}, Actual/Calculated speed limit</i>
	Validation	None
	Maximum tree depth	7
	Minimum number of cases in the parent node	15
	Minimum number of cases in the child node	3
Results	Included independent variables	<i>Calculated speed V_{crit}, Curve radius R, ACR - Accident cost rate, Road surface friction μ, Actual/Calculated speed limit, Cross slope q</i>
	Number of nodes	9
	Number of terminal nodes	5
	Depth	3

The model has a tree depth of 3, a total of 9 nodes, and 5 terminal nodes. It is particularly noteworthy that the calculated speed V_{crit} was identified as the most important variable, as evidenced by the first split in the tree structure (Figure 5).

Figure 5: BAUM Analysis Using the CRT (Classification and Regression Tree) Method: Tree Diagram

Interpretation of the Decision Tree (Figure 5):

Node 1 – Subdivision at Low Critical Speed (V_{crit})

In cases with a critical speed (V_{crit}) of ≤ 98.88 km/h, a further split is performed based on the ratio of the actual to the calculated speed limit, using a threshold value of 90.0. This variable reflects the extent to which the imposed speed limit corresponds to the dynamic driving potential of the road segment.

Within this node ($n = 168$), the overall safety situation is tense: only 11.9% of cases are classified as safe, whereas 88.1% are categorized as unsafe. The additional differentiation based on the speed limit ratio aims to identify more nuanced gradations of safety within this generally high-risk group.

Node 3 – Speed Limit ≤ 90.0 km/h

This node includes road sections where the actual speed limit does not exceed 90 km/h. Among the 38 cases analyzed, 52.6% were classified as safe and 47.4% as unsafe, resulting in an almost balanced distribution.

This group represents a transitional zone where no definitive statement about traffic safety can be made. It is likely that additional factors not explicitly considered in the model, such as sight distance, cross slope, or pavement condition, influence the safety level. A more detailed examination of these sections appears advisable from a traffic engineering perspective.

Node 4 – Speed Limit > 90 km/h

This node comprises 130 cases where the actual speed limit exceeds 90 km/h despite the relatively low critical speed. The results are unequivocal: 100% of these sections were classified as unsafe.

This constellation indicates a critical mismatch between the road's geometric characteristics and the permitted speed. In these cases, the speed appears inadequately adapted to the road geometry, resulting in a significantly increased accident risk.

Node 2 – $V_{crit} > 98.88$ km/h

Curves with a critical speed exceeding 98.88 km/h are generally considered safe within the model, a finding clearly confirmed in this node. Of the 186 cases analyzed, 98.4% were classified as safe and only 1.6% as unsafe.

To enable a finer differentiation within this predominantly safe group, the critical speed is again employed as a splitting criterion, with a threshold value of 100.12 km/h.

Node 5 – $V_{crit} \leq 100.12$ km/h

This node contains 7 cases with a critical speed slightly above the main threshold but below 100.12 km/h. The distribution here is mixed: 57.1% of cases were classified as safe and 42.9% as unsafe.

Given the absence of a clear trend, a further subdivision was carried out to allow for more precise analysis. The objective is to identify subgroups with homogeneous risk profiles even within this intermediate range.

Node 7 – $V_{crit} \leq 69.46$ km/h

This node represents road segments with particularly low critical speeds. Among the 19 cases, 94.7% were classified as unsafe.

This suggests that even within an overall "safe" context, lower critical speeds may indicate elevated risk, possibly due to local restrictions such as tight curve radii, limited sight distances, or specific hazards.

Node 8 – $V_{crit} > 69.46$ km/h

By contrast, this node also includes 19 cases where the critical speed is slightly higher. In this group, all cases (100%) were classified as safe.

Thus, the threshold of 69.46 km/h appears to represent a critical turning point beyond which traffic safety can be considered restored.

Node 6 – $V_{crit} > 100.12$ km/h

This largest and most clear-cut group in the decision tree comprises 179 cases, all of which were classified as safe (100%).

According to the model, curves with a critical speed exceeding 100.12 km/h provide very high levels of traffic safety. No further analysis or adjustment of these sections appears necessary from a safety perspective.

The results demonstrate the pivotal role of critical speed (V_{crit}) as a key predictor of traffic safety on curves. The decision tree structure enables a clear and objective differentiation between safety-critical and non-critical sections, relying on a few but highly relevant threshold values. Configurations featuring low critical speeds in conjunction with excessive speed limits appear particularly hazardous. Conversely, sections with high V_{crit} values exhibit very high safety levels. These findings offer important implications for traffic engineering interventions and speed limit adjustments.

4.4.2 CRT (Classification and Regression Tree) Method – Validation through Cross-validation

To ensure the generalizability and stability of the model, a cross-validation was performed in SPSS. The results of the cross-validation show:

- The estimation risk is 0.011, with a standard error of 0.006, for both the original model and the cross-validation.
- This suggests that the model does not exhibit overfitting and can be effectively applied to new data.
- The model's goodness of fit remains stable, whether the model is applied to the training data or to datasets modified through cross-validation.

4.5 High-Risk Curve Classification Model

4.5.1 Methodology

Since no direct measurements for the actual speed V_{act} were available, it was calculated using an empirically validated method in SPSS. Based on the difference between the speed limit and the critical speed, a correction function was introduced [Eq. 3]

$$V_{act} = \text{Tempolimit} + f \times (\text{Tempolimit} - V_{crit}) \quad (\text{Eq. 3})$$

Here, f is a scaling factor that can be derived from empirical data (e.g., the 85th percentile of speed).

- $f = 1.0$ → Drivers adhere exactly to the speed limit.

- $f = 0.85$ → Drivers, on average, exceed 85% of the difference over V_{crit} .
- $f = 0.5$ → Drivers drive exactly in the middle between the speed limit and V_{crit} .

The factor 0.85 is based on empirical traffic safety studies that show drivers often exploit 85% of the difference between the speed limit and the critical speed.

The 'High-Risk Curve Classification Model' is designed to classify curve sections based on their accident risk. The risk factor RF is defined as the ratio between actual and critical speed [Eq 4].

$$RF = \frac{V_{act}}{V_{crit}} \quad (\text{Eq. 4})$$

In this process, V_{act} , V_{crit} , μ , q , and R are used to identify high-risk curves as per Table 4.

Table 4: Classification of the Curve According to the High-Risk Curve Classification Model

Risk Factor RF	Accident Risk	Interpretation
$RF < 1.0$	Low	Actual speed is lower than critical speed
$RF \approx 1.0 - 1.2$	Medium	Drivers drive close to the critical speed
$RF > 1.2$	High	Drivers significantly exceed the critical speed

The curves were grouped based on the following parameters:

- Risk factor RF
- Curve radius R
- Road surface friction μ
- Cross slope q
- Accident cost rate ACR

4.5.2 Modeling

In the study, the High-Risk Curve Classification Model was initially developed based on classical statistical methods (CHAID decision tree) in SPSS. The CHAID model offers a clear rule structure that is easily interpretable for traffic planners. However, it is limited in modeling non-linear relationships. While this model already allowed for good classification of high-risk curves, it was decided to further develop the approach using Neural Networks (Multilayer Perceptron, MLP).

Neural Network (MLP-Perceptron)

To better capture possible non-linear dependencies, a neural network was trained with the following parameters:

- Curve radius R
- Accident cost rate ACR
- Road surface friction μ

- Cross slope q
- Actual speed V_{act}

An initial model attempt using four neurons in the hidden layer showed perfect classification performance on the training data (AUC = 1.000), but clear indications of overfitting. To improve generalization capability, a validated model with three neurons in the hidden layer was developed.

The final model uses:

- Softmax activation in the output layer (for multiclass classification)
- Hyperbolic tangent (tanh) in the hidden layer (for nonlinear activation)
- L2 regularization with a regularization parameter of $C = 0.1$
- Batch training using a scaled gradient method

The model architecture is shown in Figure 6. The connection lines represent synaptic weights: positive weights are shown in gray, negative weights in blue.

Figure 6: Neural Network (MLP-Perceptron) – Validated Model

The corresponding parameter estimates of the model can be found in Table 5.

Table 5: Parameter Estimates of the Validated Model

Predictor Variable	Hidden Layer 1			Output Layer			
	H(1:1)	H(1:2)	H(1:3)	QCL_1 = 1	QCL_1=2	QCL_1=3	QCL_1=4
Bias	-0.676	-0.126	1.969				
Curve Radius R	1.950	4.963	0.653				

Accident Cost Rate (ACR)	0.206	0.038	-0.011		
Skid Resistance μ	0.314	-0.153	-0.030		
Cross Slope q	1.183	0.146	-0.720		
Actual Speed V_{act}	0.400	-0.187	0.060		
Bias (hidden \rightarrow output)				-1.753	1.529
H(1:1)				1.411	0.574
H(1:2)				1.368	3.980
H(1:3)				0.400	0.680
					-0.640
					0.869
					-1.240
					-2.249
					-2.261
					-3.087
					2.0

The cluster distribution (Table 6) remains largely consistent, with clusters 2 and 4 again dominating. The classification table shows a test accuracy of 97.4%.

Table 6: Classification – Validated Model

Case Type	Observed	Predicted				Correct %
		1	2	3	4	
Training	1	0	1	0	0	0.0%
	2	0	111	0	0	100.0%
	3	0	0	3	1	75.0%
	4	0	0	0	124	100.0%
Test	1	0	1	0	0	0.0%
	2	0	55	0	0	100.0%
	3	0	0	1	0	100.0%
	4	0	1	1	55	96.5%
Overall						97.4%

Figure 7 shows the ROC curve of the validated model. High AUC values close to 1.000 are observed for classes 2–4, while class 1 shows slightly lower performance with an AUC of 0.716 (Table 7).

Figure 7: ROC Curve – Validated Model

Table 7: Area Under the Curve (AUC) – Validated Model

Cluster Number	AUC
1	0.716
2	0.993
3	0.999
4	1.000

The variable importance analysis (Table 8, Figure 8) confirms that Curve Radius R is the most significant predictor (normalized importance = 100%), followed by Cross Slope q (31%) and Actual Speed V_{act} (14.2%).

Table 8: Predictor Importance – Validated Model

Variable	Importance	Normalized Importance
Curve Radius R	0.631	100.0%
Accident Cost Rate (ACR)	0.034	5.5%
Skid Resistance μ	0.049	7.8%
Cross Slope q	0.196	31.0%
Actual Speed V_{act}	0.090	14.2%

Figure 8: Predictor Importance Chart – Validated Model

Conclusion of Model Comparison

The revision of the neural network model led to the following validated improvements:

- Reduction of hidden neurons to 3, resulting in a more efficient and interpretable network structure.
- Significantly lower test error rate, with misclassification reduced from 18.3% in the original model to 2.6% in the validated version.
- High discriminatory performance in risk classes 2–4, as reflected by AUC values near 1.000, despite a slightly reduced sensitivity in class 1 (AUC = 0.716).
- Improved generalization capability, as demonstrated by the lower error rate on unseen data and the successful application of 10-fold cross-validation.
- Confirmation of actual speed (V_{act}) as a relevant predictor, though its influence is outperformed by curve radius (R) and cross slope (q) in the variable importance analysis.

Through the use of L2 regularization ($C = 0.1$), cross-validation, and an optimized network architecture, the final version of the multilayer perceptron (MLP) model achieves greater robustness against overfitting and provides a substantial improvement in predictive performance compared to the initial configuration.

Table 9: Model Comparison

Feature	Original MLP Model	Optimized MLP Model
Architecture	User-defined, 1 layer, 4 neurons	User-defined, 1 layer, 3 neurons
Activation Functions	Tanh (hidden layer), Softmax (output)	Tanh (hidden layer), Softmax (output)
Training Accuracy	97.5%	99.2%
Test Accuracy	81.7%	97.4%
AUC (QCL_1 = 1)	1.000	0.716
AUC (QCL_1 = 2)	1.000	0.993
AUC (QCL_1 = 3)	1.000	0.999
AUC (QCL_1 = 4)	1.000	1.000
Most Important Variable	Curve Radius R	Curve Radius R
Regularization	None	L2 regularization (C = 0.1)
Training Method	Not specified	Batch, scaled conjugate gradient
Test Misclassification Rate	18.3%	2.6%
Interpretation	Good fit, but generalization limited (overfitting)	Improved generalization, lower misclassification

The original model is no longer shown in detail due to its confirmed overfitting behavior.

5 Results and discussion

This study examined the critical calculation speed (V_{crit}) in curves on federal roads B in two Austrian federal states. Based on a comprehensive analysis of accident statistics, geometric road data, and road conditions, it was found that traditional design speed models systematically underestimate actual accident risks. Particularly tight curve radii, insufficient cross slope, and an irregular sequence of curve radii contribute to accidents and should be more strongly considered in traffic planning.

5.1 Comparison of Different Modeling Approaches

- **Binary Logistic Regression:** The classification of curves as 'safe' or 'unsafe' was based on 354 cases. However, logistic regression yielded no statistically significant results, indicating limited suitability for capturing the complex relationships influencing curve safety.
- **Multiple Linear Regression:** Although this method showed a statistically significant effect of the accident cost rate (ACR) on the speed limit, its overall explanatory power was weak ($R^2 = 4.5\%$). Other key variables—such as curve radius, road surface friction, and cross slope—did not show significant influence.
- **BAUM Analysis (CRT Method):** This decision tree approach revealed that calculated speed (V_{crit}), curve radius (R), and accident cost rate (ACR) were the most influential variables. While more interpretable than neural networks, CRT analysis was less accurate in risk classification (AUC \approx 0.76–0.89).
- **Neural Network (Original MLP Model):** The initial multilayer perceptron achieved perfect

classification accuracy on the training set and $AUC = 1.000$ for all four clusters (QCL_1 to QCL_4). However, this result strongly indicated overfitting, as no validation was applied and generalization could not be confirmed.

- **Neural Network (Validated MLP Model):** The optimized model with 3 hidden neurons, L2 regularization, and cross-validation showed strong generalization performance with a test accuracy of 97.4% and substantially reduced misclassification (2.6%). Although sensitivity in class 1 decreased slightly ($AUC = 0.716$), the model achieved excellent performance in classes 2–4 ($AUC > 0.99$). It also confirmed the dominant influence of curve radius, followed by cross slope and actual speed (V_{act}).
- **Cluster Analysis:** Most curve sections were assigned to clusters 2 (medium risk) and 4 (very high risk). This highlights the prevalence of elevated risk levels in the examined dataset and supports the necessity of robust classification methods.

Summary:

Classical models like logistic and linear regression were not sufficient to explain the complex interplay of geometric and environmental variables. CRT analysis improved interpretability but fell short in predictive power. The validated neural network, however, combined high accuracy with generalizability, offering the most powerful and reliable classification of high-risk curves.

5.1 Implications for Practice and Policy

The findings of this study suggest that critical curve speed should become a key consideration in setting speed limits and designing traffic control measures for rural roads. Sections where critical speed (V_{crit}) is substantially lower than posted speed limits should be prioritized for targeted interventions, including dynamic speed management systems, improved signage, and friction enhancement strategies.

Policymakers should also consider integrating machine learning-based risk assessment tools into existing road safety audit frameworks to identify high-risk curves more effectively. In line with Safe System principles, infrastructure should be designed to "forgive" human errors by ensuring that road features such as curve radius and superelevation are adequately matched with expected speed behaviors, thus proactively reducing accident risk.

6 Conclusions

This study provides valuable insights into the assessment of high-risk curves and shows that an integrative analysis of geometric, vehicular dynamics, and accident-related parameters is necessary to optimize traffic safety.

Recommended Measures:

- Optimization of road infrastructure, particularly through adjusted cross slope and improved road surface friction.

- Dynamic speed regulation to enable situational adjustments of speed in curves.
- Use of modern vehicle sensors and V2I technologies to inform drivers in real-time about critical curve sections.

The developed classification models could be integrated into traffic safety-related decision systems in the future to proactively reduce accident risks. Future research should focus on an expanded data set, the integration of real-time driving behavior data, and machine learning techniques to further improve the precision of risk assessment.

Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

During the preparation of this work, the author used ChatGPT-4o in order to improve readability and language. After using this tool/service, the author reviewed and edited the content as needed and takes full responsibility for the content of the published article.

Funding sources

This research did not receive any specific grant from funding agencies in the public, commercial, or not-for-profit sectors.

Acknowledgements:

I would especially like to express my heartfelt gratitude to the AIT – Austrian Institute of Technology, in particular to DI Michael Aleksa, AIT Project Advisor and Senior Research Engineer in Transportation Infrastructure Technologies; DI Peter Saleh, AIT Senior Research Engineer in Transportation Infrastructure Technologies; and Mr. Stephan Wittmann, AIT Research Engineer, for their valuable support.

7 References

- [1] Bauer, K. M., & Harwood, D. W. (2000). Safety effects of horizontal curve and grade combinations on rural two-lane highways (FHWA-RD-99-207). Federal Highway Administration.
<https://www.fhwa.dot.gov/publications/research/safety/13077/002.cfm>
- [2] De Oña, J., Garach, L., (2012) Accidents Prediction Model based on Speed Reduction on Spanish Two-Lane Rural Highways, *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 53, 1010-1018.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2012.09.950>.
- [3] Buddhavarapu, P., Banerjee, A., Prozzi, J.A., (2013) Influence of pavement condition on horizontal curve safety. *Accident Analysis & Prevention* 52C:9-18. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aap.2012.12.010>
- [4] Fitzpatrick, K., Carlson, P. J., Brewer, M. A., & Wooldridge, M. D. (2000). Design Speed, Operating Speed, and Posted Speed Practices (NCHRP Report 504). Transportation Research Board.
https://onlinepubs.trb.org/onlinepubs/nchrp/nchrp_rpt_504.pdf
- [5] Glennon, J. C. (1996). Effect of Roadway Geometry on Highway Safety (Report No. FHWA-RD-96-036). Federal Highway Administration.
- [6] Hall, J., Smith, K., & Littleton, P. (2009). Guide for pavement friction (NCHRP Synthesis 432). Transportation Research Board. https://onlinepubs.trb.org/onlinepubs/nchrp/nchrp_syn_432.pdf
- [7] Gillespie, T. (1992) Fundamentals of Vehicle Dynamics. SAE International, Warrendale.
<https://doi.org/10.4271/R-114>
- [8] Li, Z., Li, Y., Pan, L., Wang, W., & Xu, C. (2014). Development of a variable speed limit strategy to reduce secondary collision risks during inclement weathers. *Accident Analysis & Prevention*, 72, 134–145. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aap.2014.06.018>
- [9] Zhang, S., Abdel-Aty, M., (2022) Real-time crash potential prediction on freeways using connected vehicle data, *Analytic Methods in Accident Research*, Volume 36, 100239, ISSN 2213-6657,
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.amar.2022.100239>.
- [10] Cafiso, S., Montella, A., D'Agostino, C., Mauriello, F., Galante, F., Crash modification functions for pavement surface condition and geometric design indicators, *Accident Analysis & Prevention*, Volume 149, 2021, 105887, ISSN 0001-4575, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aap.2020.105887>.
- [11] OECD/ITF (2008). Towards Zero: Ambitious Road Safety Targets and the Safe System Approach. Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development, International Transport Forum.
<https://fevr.ngo/wp-content/uploads/2017/12/Towards-Zero-OECD-PDF-57-MB.pdf>
- [12] Wilde, G. J. S. (1994). Target Risk: Dealing with the danger of death, disease and damage in everyday decisions. PDE Publications, Toronto.

- [13] DeJoy, David M. (1996) Theoretical models of health behavior and workplace self-protective behavior, *Journal of Safety Research*, Volume 27, Issue 2, 1996, Pages 61-72, ISSN 0022-4375, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0022-4375\(96\)00007-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/0022-4375(96)00007-2).
- [14] RVS 03.03.23, 2014. Alignment and Geometric Road Design. Austrian Research Association for Roads, Railways and Transport (FSV), Vienna.
- [15] Vogel, N., 2025. Accidents on rural state roads B 2012-2023 by accident types (curve accidents). Statistic Austria, Vienna. (Email dated 27.01.2025)
- [16] AIT, 2025. Austrian Institute of Technology, RoadSTAR. <https://www.ait.ac.at/en/labs/roadstar>
- [17] FGSV 316/1, 2003. Guideline for the Analysis of Road Traffic Accidents, Part 1: Managing and Analyzing Accident Type Cards. FGSV - Research Association for Roads and Traffic, Cologne.